

Reproduction and Evaluation: Web2Text Boilerplate Removal

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Abstract. The novel “Web2Text” approach for HTML boilerplate removal using a hidden Markov model and CNNs theoretically suggests a solid performance based on the considered *CleanEval 2007* in comparison to alternative approaches. Despite a rather extensive source code documentation and guidelines by the authors, reproduction of this algorithm involved several bugs and obstacles, yet, the feature selection and CNN scripts could still be successfully implemented with the obtained results being highly similar to the original outcomes but not entirely equivalent. Whereas the retrained and 5-fold CNN could be reproduced quite similarly to the original outcomes, particularly original and 5-fold recall produced more pronounced deviations.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Markov, CNN, CDOM, Boilerplate Removal, Feature Extraction

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1 INTRODUCTION

Within the following lines, a reproduction attempt as well as a corresponding documentation and evaluation for the research paper “Web2Text: Deep Structured Boilerplate Removal” by Vogels, Ganea and Eickhoff [1] will be made.

Thereby, the exact process for boilerplate removal as presented in the document is adhered to including HTML text pre-processing, block segmentation, feature extraction, CNN modeling as well as inferring for the appropriated CleanEval data set as well as the statistical significance of this approach compared to alternative algorithms in that regard.

2 WEB2TEXT PAPER: OVERVIEW

As HTML boilerplate removal represents an integral task for a variety of different application fields, the paper authors have proposed a novel algorithm in that context called “Web2Text” using a hidden Markov model on top of DOM tree features based on CNNs. Thereby, a training and evaluation based on the relatively common *CleanEval 2007* data set was considered as well as contrasted in comparison with similar approaches.

2.1 Approach of Web2Text Algorithm

- (1) Initially, the raw Web HTML text input to be transformed by the algorithm is parsed as a Document Object Model (DOM tree) as well as respective empty nodes or nodes with only minor content removed while single child parent nodes are merged with their respective child.
- (2) Considering the web pages in terms of blocks labeled as either *main content* or *boilerplate*, the corresponding DOM leaves are supposed to constitute the respective blocks.
- (3) For the properties of the nodes, the paper author distinguish between so-called *block features* and *edge features* whereby the former constitute information on each block of a Web page while the latter considers information on each pair of neighboring blocks.
- (4) Subsequently, text blocks are assigned so-called *unary potentials* essentially representing probabilities of the block in question either being main content or boilerplate which should

sum up to one. In contrast, *pairwise potentials* constitute the transition probabilities of text block pairs and should also sum up to one. These potentials are consecutively modeled using 5-layer CNNs as well as employing drop-out regularization while minimizing cross-entropy for these potentials.

- (5) Lastly, the joint prediction of most probable sequence of labels is retrieved using a hidden Markov model being maximized while using the Viterbi algorithm.

2.2 Experimental setup

In assessing the performance as well as statistical significance to boilerplate remove of their novel “Web2Text” approach, the paper authors appropriated the following experimental set-up which should - theoretically - be sufficient to reproduce their respective outcomes with regard to the relative effectiveness of their model:

- Training data: *CleanEval 2007* as one of the largest publicly available datasets for boilerplate removal testing was considered whereby a split into 531 training, 58 validation as well as 148 test pages was considered by the study researchers instead of the original 55p - 5p - 676p partitioning. Additionally, in order to generate further training examples, the alignment between source and cleaned text as well as block labels are recovered in a *divide-et-impera* manner.
- CNNs: When appropriating the 5-layered CNNs as previously described, factors such as ReLU non-linearity between layers, filter sizes of (50,50,50,10,2) for unary as well as (50,50,50,10,4) for pairwise potentials with a stride of 1, padding of 0 and kernel sizes of (1,1,3,3,3) respectively were considered. Thereby, the unary outputs constitute sequences of 2 values per block which are - in turn - normalized using soft-max. Moreover, for the dropout regularization a rate of 0.2 as well as a weight decay with rate 10^{-4} are included.

2.3 Algorithm performance

When assessing the effectiveness of their “Web2Text” algorithm in the given context, the researchers compared their novel approach to competing methods of content extraction (especially for use upon Web data) such as BTE, Unfluff or Conditional Random Field. Thereby, the respective performance outcomes were evaluated on the basis of the *CleanEval 2007* data set considering both the original training-validation-test set split as well as their modified equivalent as presented below.

Original Test				
Method	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
CRF	0.8	0.88	0.81	0.84
BTE	0.75	0.76	0.84	0.80
default-ext	0.79	0.89	0.74	0.81
article-ext	0.67	0.89	0.50	0.64
largest-ext	0.59	0.93	0.33	0.48
Unfluff	0.68	0.90	0.51	0.65
Web2Text	0.86	0.87	0.90	0.88

Hence, one may discern that solid results in terms of accuracy, recall and F1 scores were achieved in comparison with popular baselines while the additional benefits of hidden Markov compared to the unary CNN approach are to be considered as rather minuscule.

Consequentially, our main point of emphasis within the current report resides in attempting to reproduce the entire algorithmic procedures as well as to retrieve similar performance outcomes based on the considered *CleanEval 2007* data set. In that context, the competing algorithms in the

field of boilerplate removal as well as the different task of ad-hoc document retrieval with the *ClueWeb12 collection* will be explicitly excluded from our scrutiny.

3 REPRODUCTION OF PAPER

When attempting to replicate the described “Web2Text“ algorithm and to apply it upon the described *CleanEval 2007* data set in order to objectively measure and evaluate the respective outcomes and results generated by the paper authors, one may integrally discern that the entire source code for the paper under scrutiny as well as the data set considered was publicly provided by the researchers on GitHub.

3.1 Source code instructions by authors

As an accompanying note to their files, the paper authors also presented several guidelines, pre-requisites, usage information as well as a recipe for successful implementation and reproduction of their algorithm and results in addition to further notes within a Blog post.

Essentially, after having all the stipulated installation pre-requisites (precisely *Scala/SBT v1.3.3*, *Python 3.7*, *Tensorflow 1.15*, *Numpy 1.18*, *NVIDIA CUDA Toolkit v10.0*, *Java >v1.8*), the researchers continue to basically explain the folder structure and require the user to run the following commands for performing HTML feature extraction:

```
sbt "runMain ch.ethz.dalab.web2text.ExtractPageFeatures result/input.html
result/step_1_extracted_features"
python src\main\python\main.py classify result\step_1_extracted_features
result/step_2_classified_labels
sbt "runMain ch.ethz.dalab.web2text.ApplyLabelsToPage result/input.html
result/step_2_classified_labels result/step_3_applied_labels"
```

Moreover, following the setting of concrete variables and files within the Python part, training the aforementioned CNNs upon CSV documents and evaluating them accordingly with regard to competing approaches can be carried out - according to the paper authors - by considering the following executions in Terminal:

```
python3 data/convert_scala_csv.py
python3 main.py train_unary
python3 main.py train_edge
python3 main.py test_structured
```

3.2 Performing feature extraction

For a start, before even attempting to perform the respective instructions as proposed by the paper authors, one may already discern that certain key pieces of information are missing. For instance, despite mentioning that a MacBook 2.8 GHz Intel i5 was used the run the scripts within the context of run times, no explicit details regard Operating Systems, GPU hardware and the like were provided.

After having downloaded the respective GitHub repository [2] as made publicly available by the paper authors and installing the corresponding requirements stipulated, running the first line of code in Terminal for starting the HTML feature extraction process as proposed already failed. Following some additional trial-and-error as well as searching the web for potential solutions, it turns out that explicitly JDK v8 is required for performing the respective *.scala* documents - a fact which was not previously named.

Additionally, when checking the respective underlying code, one may also need to create a respective *results* folder within the root directory and place the corresponding HTML Web documents

to be transformed in it which - in our case - alluded to selected pages from the *CleanEval 2007* data set.

Moreover, before being finally able to run the respective commands described by the paper authors for the sake of HTML feature extraction, changing the *ApplyLabelsToPage.scala* document in line 41 while replacing the expression `Source.fromFile(filename).getLines.mkString` with `Util.loadFile(filename)` proved to be necessary as well.

Other libraries which actually turned out to be integral for replicating the outcomes and results generated by the researchers include the Python packages *future* for feature extraction as well as the *click* within the context of training the CNN model.

However, having consulted multiple resources relating to the respective GitHub repository as well as implementing the bug fixes and solutions as presented above, the corresponding scripts performing feature extraction upon user-selected HTML files and subsequently generating resulting CSV files on top of that could be successfully implemented.

Additionally, the preparation of features for other methods mentioned in the paper was attempted, however, multiple issues have occurred regarding the script executions and the only one which ran successfully was the Unfluff method. Hence, we decided not to recreate the remaining other methods results.

3.3 CNN modeling

Similar to the feature extraction part of their novel “Web2Text“ approach for boilerplate removal, the paper authors likewise provided evidently detailed instructions regarding how to train the respective CNNs and evaluate their respective performance upon the *CleanEval 2007* test set.

Hence, when trying to replicate the results generated by the researchers within the CNN modeling part of their work, we focused explicitly on validating the robustness of the modeling approach. Since the model training/validation and testing was done on a predefined (possibly cherry-picked) and static split of the data, our main priority was to confirm that the choice of data wasn’t introducing a bias to the evaluation at hand.

However, following a check of the CHECKPOINT_DIR variable within the `main.py` file for adjusting the training weights as described within the instructing, running the initial `python3 data/convert_scala_csv.py` for CNN model training already failed.

As it turned out, an error regarding `Exception in thread "main" java.lang.OutOfMemoryError: GC overhead limit exceeded` occurred which could be resolved by manually increasing the heap size on our local machine in order to prevent potential RAM overflows.

Nonetheless, following the implementation of the described measure to alleviate some of the bugs that occurred, we managed to successfully run the CNN retraining and evaluation part of the source code as described by the paper authors and could - consequentially - measure the respective performance outcomes upon the *CleanEval 2007* data set for the novel “Web2Text“ algorithm.

3.4 Evaluation of reproduction outcomes

Hence, following the successful implementation of the “Web2Text“ feature extraction algorithms as well as the corresponding CNN model re-training and performance evaluation of the paper under scrutiny, our main findings and key numerical results in that context are presented in the table below.

Original Test				
Method	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Web2Text	0.86	0.87	0.90	0.88
Modified Test				
Method	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Web2Text Re	0.84	0.86	0.88	0.87
Web2Text 5F	0.84	0.86	0.86	0.86

Table 1. Reproduction results.

As already mentioned previously, our main point of emphasis resided on reproducing the respective CNN model performance outcomes of the “Web2Text” approach upon the considered *CleanEval 2007* data set and thereby confirm as well as reproduce and replicate the integral underlying insights of the research work at hand. Particularly, evaluating the competing approaches such as BTE, Unfluff or CRF as well as measuring the impact on ad-hoc retrieval performance were explicitly excluded from our scrutiny.

With “Web2text Re” and “Web2Text 5F”, two evaluation approaches are presented whereby the former uses the exact same experimental setup and splitting the data to generally confirm the values from the paper, and the latter also appropriates an equivalent experimental setup but calculates the performance metrics based on a 5-fold average. With the notable exception of the precision metric, we were not able to solidly confirm the published results. Both of our attempts slightly under-performed in comparison to the original paper outcomes whereas the 5-fold average and original split perform similarly with a marginally lower value for the 5-fold case. Whether this deviation from the published result is significant enough remains questionable since the performance compared to the other benchmarks is still substantially better.

Given this rather similar performance regarding the overall outcome, a noteworthy difference between our execution of the original approach and the 5-fold average was seen during model training. Fig. 1 shows the development of the F2 scores on the training and validation data respectively for the unary and edge CNN. While the performance on the train set of the 5-fold and single run match, a clear under-performance of the single run with respect to the validation data may be discerned. While normally hinting towards over-fitting of the model, one may rule that out since the performance on the test data did not exhibit this behavior.

Fig. 1. Model training development original vs. 5-fold

Given the fact that the significant performance difference in the validation set during model training does not affect the overall outcome and may be caused by the comparably small validation set size, one may characterize this instance as a noteworthy but rather meaningless. Hence, essentially we were able to reproduce the results of the paper to some degree, even though small deviations were detected which may be caused by the authors' explicit choice of neglecting cross-validated checks.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, reproducing the exact results as presented in the paper was not entirely possible within the context of our effort, yet, the results are quite close. Particularly, issues regarding the reproduction have occurred which were mainly caused by the lack of source code documentation and software requirements from the side of the paper author. Moreover, within the context of the modified test, our retrained and 5-fold CNN models are quite equivalent to the original one while the biggest difference resides between the original recall and 5-fold recall.

REFERENCES

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